

DIPLOMA

TA'LIM FIDOYILARI

RESPUBLIKA ILMIY JURNALIDA

Sherzod Mirmakhmudov

**LAWMAKING IN THE STATES OF UZBEKISTAN AND SWEDEN:
COMPARATIVE LEGAL ANALYSIS**

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

Bosh muharrir:
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